

MALNUTRITION RISK AMONG THE ELDERLY IN SELECTED BARANGAYS OF SAN MARIANO, ISABELA: A BASIS FOR NUTRITION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Elderly malnutrition is an increasingly significant public health concern especially among the aging population due to its association with adverse health outcomes, physical decline, functional impairment, greater dependency, and higher healthcare utilization. Despite being preventable, elderly malnutrition in the remains underdiagnosed and inadequately managed especially in the primary care setting due to the lack of routine nutritional assessment in the community. This study aimed to determine the malnutrition risk and identify sociodemographic and health-related factors associated with nutritional status among the elderly population from selected barangays of San Mariano. Using a descriptive cross-sectional study and the Revised Mini Nutritional Assessment – Short Form (MNA-SF®, version 2), malnutrition as well as malnutrition risk were assessed among 536 elderly respondents from selected barangays of San Mariano. After data validation, frequencies and percentages were used to summarize the demographic profiles while summation determined MNA scores and malnutrition risk. Chi-square tests assessed the differences in nutritional determinants as well as malnutrition risk across profile variables at 0.05 significance level, with Bonferroni post-hoc tests to control Type I error. Findings revealed a relatively low prevalence of malnutrition (4.9%) among participants but substantial proportion of malnutrition risk (41%). Statistical analyses showed significant differences in the determinants of malnutrition and malnutrition risk when grouped according to profile variables. These findings underscore the need for routine nutritional screening and the development of targeted, evidence-based interventions within the community to help improve nutritional outcomes and achieve healthier aging among older adults.

Keywords: *Geriatric Health, Elderly Malnutrition, Malnutrition Risk Screening, Mini Nutritional Assessment – Short Form (MNA-SF), Community Nutrition*

INTRODUCTION

Progressive malnutrition is defined as a gradual, worsening decline in nutritional status marked by a sustained deficit in energy, protein, and other essential nutrients over time. It is frequently a chronic or disease-related condition in which the body's nutrient intake fails to meet its metabolic demands, resulting in depleted body reserves, functional decline, and, in many cases, significant weight loss. It becomes more common in the elderly because it is driven by age-related changes (diminished ability to taste foods, chewing problems, slower digestion) and compounding factors like chronic diseases, social isolation, depression, poverty, and mobility issues, leading to increased frailty, higher hospitalizations, and mortality.

The risk of malnutrition increases with advancing age, and poor nutritional status has been identified as a strong predictor of adverse clinical outcomes among older adults. Although largely preventable, malnutrition in the elderly remains underdiagnosed and inefficiently managed within healthcare systems, underscoring the urgent need for improved strategies for its detection, prevention, and management.

Regular nutritional screening and assessment of malnutrition risk among the elderly is critical for the early detection and timely intervention of progressive malnutrition. It is commonly conducted at the hospital setting to help improve in-patient outcomes. This practice, however, is rarely integrated into standard geriatric care in the primary care setting due to the lack of routine and standardized nutritional assessment protocols implemented. As a result, the true burden of malnutrition is frequently underestimated, progressive undernutrition is undetected and evidence-based nutritional programs are inconsistently implemented.

Background of the Study

According to the United Nations, individuals aged 60 years and above represent the fastest-growing segment of the global population, with the number of older persons around one billion and rising rapidly (United Nations, 2017). This demographic shift is largely attributed to advancements in healthcare that have added approximately five years to the global life expectancy. Moreover, projections by the United Nations Population Division indicate that by 2050, the number of people aged 60 and above will surpass the population of adolescents aged 10 to 24 years (2.1 billion versus 2.0 billion) (United Nations, 2017).

In the Philippines, the proportion of elderly individuals has also been rising at a rate that exceeds that of the general population. At the beginning of the 21st century, there were approximately 4.6 million Filipinos aged 60 years and older, comprising about six percent of the total population. By 2023, this number had grown to 10.3 million, accounting for 8.8 percent of the national population, and is projected to reach 16.5

percent by 2050 (Tandang et al., 2020). This demographic shift is mirrored in rural municipalities such as San Mariano, Isabela, where the proportion of elderly residents increased from 3,179 (5.74%) in 2020 to 4,327 (7.0%) in 2023. This upward trend is expected to continue, driven by a declining birth rate—from 13.9 in 2020 to 13.0 in 2023—making San Mariano’s population, like the rest of the nation and the world, increasingly aged.

Aging is accompanied by a marked increase in functional dependence and disability (Jiang & Li, 2024). These conditions lead to greater healthcare utilization, higher medical expenditures, and increased mortality rates (Vaish et al., 2020). Older age itself is a significant predictor of malnutrition, with the oldest-old and centenarian groups being the most vulnerable (Zhu et al., 2025). Physiological and appetite-related changes associated with aging negatively affect food intake and nutrient absorption, predisposing older adults to undernutrition and its complications. Despite these challenges, the full extent of undernutrition among the elderly remains underrecognized, as most national and local nutrition programs focus primarily on children, adolescents, and pregnant or lactating women.

In San Mariano, the increase in the number of malnourished and nutritionally at-risk older adults frequently go undetected due to the absence of a standardized nutritional screening or assessment tool. Based on the San Mariano Municipal Health Office Annual Reports, chronic malnutrition and failure to thrive among the elderly have emerged as significant public health concerns, ranking as the second leading cause of mortality in 2022 and the eighth in 2023 (San Mariano Local Government Unit, 2022/2023). Currently, healthcare personnel rely primarily on Body Mass Index (BMI) to assess the nutritional status of older adults, despite its well-documented limitations. This approach identifies only those with a BMI below 18.5 kg/m² as undernourished, thereby failing to detect individuals who are at nutritional risk. Furthermore, the only available data from the Field Health Services Information System (FHSIS) concerning the nutritional status of elderly individuals (aged 60 years and above) pertains to those classified as overweight or obese, with no data available on underweight individuals. In the absence of an established nutritional assessment process for senior citizens, the true prevalence of undernutrition and nutritional risk among the elderly remains undetermined. Consequently, nutrition-related programs targeting this age group remain limited in both scope and reach.

Assessing the nutritional status of older adults is essential for promoting longevity and enhancing quality of life (Volkert et al., 2019). In addition, determining the risk of developing malnutrition among the older population, enables early identification of vulnerable individuals that can prevent functional decline, reduce hospitalizations and improve overall health outcomes (Cederholm et al., 2019; Dent et al., 2019). Among the tools available, the Mini Nutritional Assessment – Short Form (MNA-SF®, version 2) is one of the most widely used and internationally recommended instruments in identifying malnutrition and risk of malnutrition among older populations (Kaiser et al., 2009; Rubenstein et al., 2001). However, it is rarely applied in rural communities such as San Mariano. This leads to paucity of accurate, context-specific data necessary for the local health authorities in designing and implementing effective, evidence-based nutrition programs for the elderly.

This study addresses these gaps by conducting a baseline assessment on malnutrition risk among the elderly population from selected barangays of San Mariano by using the validated and internationally recommended screening tool, the Revised Mini Nutritional Assessment – Short Form (MNA-SF® version 2) (Kaiser et al., 2009; Volkert et al., 2019). The tool will help identify individuals at risk among the population as well determine the contributing factors to elderly malnutrition within the area.

The findings will be used to craft a targeted and evidence-based nutrition program that will help improve geriatric care in San Mariano as well as promote healthy aging thereby reducing nutrition-related morbidity and premature mortality within the municipality.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Sex
 - 1.2 Civil Status
 - 1.3 Age
 - 1.4 Residence
 - 1.5 Ethnicity
2. What is the risk of malnutrition among the elderly from selected barangays of San Mariano, Isabela?
3. Is there a significant difference between the determinants of malnutrition among the elderly from selected barangays of San Mariano when grouped according to profile?
4. Is there a significant difference between in the risk of malnutrition among the elderly from selected barangays of San Mariano when grouped according to profile?
5. What nutrition program for the elderly can be crafted and proposed for implementation to address the risk of malnutrition?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive cross-sectional design to assess malnutrition risk among elderly residents of selected barangays in San Mariano, Isabela, Philippines. The cross-sectional design was selected to provide snapshot of malnutrition risk and its determinants at a single point in time, enabling the examination of associations between malnutrition risk and demographic variables without manipulating the study environment.

The study was conducted in five out of 36 barangays of San Mariano, specifically Barangays Binatug, Bitabian, Casala, Gangalan and Ueg – randomly selected to represent diverse economic and demographic characteristics within the municipality. San Mariano is a first-class but rural municipality located in the eastern portion of Isabela. As of 2024, it has an estimated population of 62, 937 residents across 14,801 households, with agriculture and fishing as primary sources of livelihood.

The study population consisted of 536 senior citizens (aged ≥ 60 years) registered in selected barangays. Participants were recruited using convenience sampling, based on accessibility and willingness to participate. The inclusion criteria were: (1) age 60 years or older, (2) residency in the selected barangays for at least six months and (3) voluntary provision of informed consent. Elderly respondents residing in the barangays for less than six months or non-residents were excluded. The table below summarizes the population distribution across barangays:

Barangays	Population
Binatug	53
Bitabian	110
Casala	186
Gangalan	121
Ueg	66
TOTAL	536

Participants demographic data were collected using the first section of the survey instrument. These included age, civil status, place of residence and ethnicity. (Detailed demographic distributions are presented in the Results section.)

Nutritional status was assessed using the Mini Nutritional Assessment – Short Form (MNA[®]- SF), a validated screening tool developed by Kaiser and colleagues in 2009. This tool is widely used to identify malnutrition and risk of malnutrition in older adults and has demonstrated strong validity and reliability across diverse populations. The instrument consists of six items which evaluate the following: (1) Decline in food intake over the past three months, (2) Involuntary weight loss over the past three months, (3) Mobility, (4) Psychological stress or acute disease in the past three months, (5) Neuropsychological problems (dementia or depression) and (6) Anthropometric measurements (Body mass index or calf circumference).

The instrument comprises two sections. The first section collects demographic data. The second section assess nutritional status using a 3- and 4-point Likert type scale, Total scores range from 0 to 14. The scores were interpreted as follows:

MNA SCREENING SCORE

- 12 – 14 points
- 8 – 11 points
- 7 points or below

MALNUTRITION RISK

- No Risk (Normal Nutritional Status)
- At risk of malnutrition
- Malnourished

Two versions of the MNA[®]- SF were utilized: the MNA-SF-BMI (using Body mass index measurement) and the MNA-SF-CC (using calf-circumference when BMI was not available). Both versions use identical cut-off points. Permission to use the MNA[®]- SF was obtained from the Mapi Research Trust, the authorized distributor for the Nestlé

Nutrition Institute. The MNA[®]- SF has been extensively validated in older adult population and is considered a reliable screening tool for malnutrition.

Data collection as conducted from July 1, 2024 to August 30, 2024 through face – to- face interviews conducted by trained community health workers. The following steps were undertaken: (1) Institutional and Barangay Approval. Written permission was obtained from the Office of the Municipal Mayor and from the Punong Barangays of the selected barangays (2) Instrument Authorization. License to use the MNA[®]- SF was secured from Mapi Research Trust. (3) Sampling Frame Acquisition. Master lists of registered senior citizens from the selected barangays. (4) Enumerator Training. Community health workers were trained on ethical procedures and proper administration of the MNA[®]- SF questionnaire. (5) Informed Consent. Participants were informed of the study purpose, procedures and confidentiality measures and written informed consent was obtained. (6) Primary Data Collection. Face-to-face interviews were conducted using the MNA[®]- SF questionnaire. (7) Anthropometric Measurements. Height and weight were measured using Detecto 339 Mechanical Physician’s Scale at the Rural Health Unit or Barangay Health Stations. When BMI could not be obtained, calf circumference was measured and lastly (8) Data Validation and Preparation. Completed questionnaires were reviewed for completeness and data were coded and entered into a spreadsheet for analysis.

Data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage distribution) were computed to summarize demographic characteristics and nutritional status (including malnutrition risk). MNA[®]- SF scores were calculated by summing item scores to determine malnutrition risk.

Inferential analysis included Chi-square test of independence to examine differences in malnutrition determinants and nutritional status (including malnutrition risk) across demographic groups. A significance level of 0.05 was used for hypothesis testing. When significant differences were observed, the Bonferroni post-hoc test was applied to control Type I error and identify specific group differences.

This study focused on elderly individuals aged 60 years and above residing in five selected barangays of San Mariano, Isabela. Nutritional status was assessed using the MNA[®]-SF instrument, and significant differences in malnutrition determinants and malnutrition risk across demographic variables were examined.

The following limitations were observed in this study: (1) Cross-sectional design limited the causal inference and only provided a snapshot of nutritional status at a single point in time, (2) Convenience sampling restricts generalizability of findings to the broader elderly population, (3) Self-reported data on food intake and weight loss may be subject to recall bias and (4) Anthropometric measurements limitations occurred when BMI could not be obtained, requiring the use of calf-circumference as an alternative.

RESULTS

Part 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex, civil status, age, residence and ethnicity.

Table 1.
Respondents Profile According as to Demographic

Sex	f	%
Male	194	36.2
Female	342	63.8
Civil Status	f	%
Single	7	1.3
Married	459	85.6
Widow/Widower	70	13.1
Age	f	%
60-69 Years Old	294	54.9
70-79 Years Old	174	32.5
80-89 Years Old	64	11.9
90 Years old and above	4	0.7
Residence (Barangay)	f	%
Bitabian	110	20.5
Binatug	53	9.9
Casala	186	34.7
Gangalan	121	22.6
Ueg	66	12.3
Ethnicity	f	%
Ilocano	424	79.1
Ybanag	81	15.1
Ifugao	16	3.0
Agta	4	0.7
Tagalog	11	2.1

Data shows that in terms of sex, majority of the respondents were female (63.8 %) while the male respondents comprised of 36.2% of. This finding shows that the population is predominated by elderly females.

With regards to civil status, majority of the respondents were ware married (85.6%) while the least were single (1.3%). In terms of age, more than half of the respondents belonged to the 60 to 69 years old group (54.9 %) followed by those aged 70–79 years old (32.5%), 80–89 years old (11.9%), and only a small fraction aged 90 years and above (0.7%). Based on residence, most respondents were from Barangay Casala (34.7%), followed by Gangalan (22.6%), Bitabian (20.5%), Ueg (12.3%), and Binatug (9.9%). This showed an uneven distribution of respondents among the barangays. Finally, in terms of ethnicity, most respondents were Ilocano (79.1%) followed by Ybanag (15.1%), Ifugao (3.0%), Tagalog (2.1%). Minimal fraction belongs to the Agra grout at 0.7. The

predominance of Ilocano respondents reflects the ethnic composition of San Mariano, Isabela, where Ilocano remains the dominant ethnolinguistic group.

Overall, the demographic profile reveals that the elderly population in the selected barangays of San Mariano is largely composed of married Ilocano females aged 60–69 years, residing mostly in Barangay Casala.

Part 2. Risk of Malnutrition Among Respondents

Table 2 presents the frequency distribution of elderly respondents across selected barangays according to their level of malnutrition risk, as determined using the Revised Mini Nutritional Assessment–Short Form (MNA®-SF). The table also shows the proportion of older adults classified as having normal nutritional status (no risk), at risk of malnutrition, or malnourished, allowing for a comparative view of nutritional health across different barangays.

Table 2
Distribution of Respondents from Selected Barangays of San Mariano, Isabela
Based on Malnutrition Risk

Barangay	Normal (No Risk)		At Risk		Malnourished		Total	
	F	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
Bitabian	38	7.1 %	59	11.0%	13	2.4%	110	20.5%
Binatug	18	3.4 %	28	5.2%	7	1.3%	53	9.9%
Casala	104	19.4%	73	13.6%	9	1.7%	186	34.7%
Gangalan	77	14.4%	43	8.0 %	1	0.2%	121	22.6%
Ueg	48	9.0 %	17	3.2%	1	0.2%	66	12.3%
Total	285	53.2%	220	41.0%	31	5.8%	536	

The results indicate that 285 individuals (53.2%) of the elderly respondents were classified as having normal nutritional status with minimal or no risk of developing malnutrition. Meanwhile, 220 respondents (41.0%) were identified as being at risk of developing malnutrition with the highest proportion from Barangay Casala at 13.6 %. Finally, there are 31 respondents (5.8%) were classified as malnourished and Barangay Bitabian accounted for the largest number of malnourished elderlies with 13 individuals (2.4%).

Part 3. 1 Malnutrition Determinants Among Respondents

Table 3 shows the frequency of the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA®) Short Form nutritional screening variables, considered in this study as malnutrition determinants, among senior citizens from selected barangays of San Mariano. The variables included the following: (A) decline in food intake over the past three months, (B) involuntary weight loss during the last three months, (C) decreased mobility (not being able to get out of the house), (D) suffering from psychological stress or acute disease in the past 3 months, (E) having neuropsychological problems (mild dementia) and (F) having a body mass index of less than 19.

Table 3
Determinants of Malnutrition Among the Elderly from Selected Barangays of San Mariano using the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA®) Short Form

Variables	Normal (No Risk)		At Risk of Malnutrition		Malnourished	
	F	%	f	%	f	%
Decline in food intake over the past 3 months						
Severe Decrease	0	0	1	0.20	3	0.60
Moderate Decrease	51	9.50	130	24.30	28	5.20
No decrease	234	43.70	89	16.60	0	0.00
Involuntary weight loss during the last 3 months						
Weight loss greater than 3 kg.	0	0	0	0	3	0.60
Does not know	1	0.20	27	5.00	14	2.60
Weight loss between 1 to 3 kg.	58	10.80	122	22.80	14	2.60
No weight loss	226	42.20	71	13.20	0	0
Mobility						
Bed or chair bound	5	0.90	14	2.60	5	0.90
Able to get out of bed	279	52.10	206	38.40	26	4.90
Goes out	1	0.20	0	0	0	0
Suffering from psychological stress or acute disease in the past 3 months						
Yes	2	0.40	31	5.80	20	3.70
No	283	52.80	189	35.30	11	2.10
Neuropsychological problems						
Severe dementia or depression	0	0	1	0.20	0	0
Mild dementia	11	2	35	6.50	16	3.00
No psychological problem	274	51.10	184	34.30	15	2.80
Body Mass Index						
Less than 19	0	0.00	102	19.00	27	5.00
19 to less than 21	34	6.30	83	15.50	4	0.70
21 to less than 23	81	15.10	25	4.70	0	0
23 or greater	170	31.70	10	1.90	0	0

Based on the above table, thirty-one (31) respondents (5.8%) who screened as malnourished reported decline in food intake as well as involuntary weight loss within the last three months and had limited mobility. However, eleven (11) respondents who were malnourished denied of suffering from psychological stress or acute disease within the last 3 months. In addition, among the 31 identified malnourished respondents, sixteen (16) or 3% had mild dementia while fifteen (15) denied of suffering from neuropsychological problems.

Malnutrition risk was also prevalent among the respondents, and was recorded at forty-one percent (41%) in this study. Among the elderly with malnutrition risk, there were eighty-nine (89) respondents (16.6%) who had no decline in food intake over the past 3 months, seventy-one (71) respondents (13.2%) who did not suffer from involuntary weight loss, one hundred eighty-nine (189) respondents (35.3 %) had no psychological stress or acute disease in the past 3 months. There were also one hundred two (102) respondents (19.0 %) who had a Body mass index of less than 19 while a total of one hundred eighteen (118) respondents (22.1 %) had Body Mass Indices greater than 19.

Part 3.2 Significant Differences in Determinants of Malnutrition by Demographic Profile

In this study, Chi-square tests of independence were used to examine whether a significant difference exists between the determinants of malnutrition specifically decline in food intake over the past 3 months, involuntary or unintentional weight loss during the last 3 months, mobility, presence of psychological stress or acute disease in the past 3 months, presence of neuro-psychological condition in the past 3 months and body mass index when grouped to demographic profile of sex, age group, civil status, place of residence and ethnicity. Chi-Square Tests for Independence were performed for each indicator. The results were presented in the Table 4 below.

Table 4.
Chi-Square Test of Independence on the Determinants of malnutrition when grouped according to profile variables

Decline in food intake within the past three months			
Profile Variables	χ^2	Df	p-value
Sex	22.971	2	<0.001
Civil Status	17.367	4	0.002
Age	69.119	6	<0.001
Residence	26.283	8	<0.001
Ethnicity	14.372	8	0.073
Involuntary Weight loss in the last three months			
Profile Variables	χ^2	Df	p-value
Sex	7.664	3	0.053
Civil Status	10.998	6	0.088
Age	9.798	9	0.367
Residence	12.154	12	0.096
Ethnicity	4.525	12	0.972
Mobility			
Profile Variables	χ^2	Df	p-value
Sex	2.285	2	0.319
Civil Status	2.185	4	0.702
Age	6.594	6	0.360
Residence	6.702	8	0.216
Ethnicity	1.206	8	0.997
Presence of psychological stress or acute disease within the last three months			
Profile Variables	χ^2	Df	p-value
Sex	0.432	1	0.511

Civil Status	0.297	2	0.862
Age	3.94	3	0.268
Residence	2.274	4	0.114
Ethnicity	3.067	4	0.110
Presence of Neuropsychiatric Problems			
Profile Variable	χ^2	Df	p-value
Sex	4.991	2	0.082
Civil Status	3.271	4	0.325
Age	9.694	6	0.268
Residence	11.911	8	0.155
Ethnicity	6.624	8	0.578
Body Mass Index			
Profile Variables	χ^2	Df	p-value
Sex	5.194	3	0.158
Civil Status	17.122	6	0.009
Age	26.451	9	0.002
Residence	28.965	12	0.004
Ethnicity	7.579	12	0.817

The results revealed there is no significant difference among the profile variables based on the decline in food intake over the past three months across several demographic factors. Specifically, reduced food intake differed significantly by sex ($\chi^2 (2) = 22.971$, $p < 0.001$), civil status ($\chi^2 (4) = 17.367$, $p = 0.002$), age ($\chi^2 (6) = 69.119$, $p < 0.001$), and place of residence ($\chi^2 (8) = 26.283$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that certain demographic groups were more likely to experience decreased food consumption.

In contrast, there were no significant differences observed in the occurrence of involuntary weight loss, suggesting that weight loss was relatively uniform across sex, age, civil status, place of residence, and ethnicity. Similarly, mobility status did not differ significantly across any profile variables, including sex ($\chi^2(2) = 2.285$, $p = 0.319$), civil status ($\chi^2(4) = 2.185$, $p = 0.702$), age ($\chi^2(6) = 6.594$, $p = 0.360$), place of residence ($\chi^2(8) = 6.702$, $p = 0.216$), or ethnicity ($\chi^2(8) = 1.206$, $p = 0.997$).

Furthermore, psychological stress, acute disease, and neuropsychiatric problems showed no significant differences across demographic groups, indicating these outcomes were relatively consistent among respondents. Finally, Body Mass Index (BMI) exhibited significant differences based on civil status ($\chi^2 (6) = 17.122$, $p = 0.009$), age ($\chi^2 (9) = 26.451$, $p = 0.002$), and place of residence ($\chi^2 (12) = 28.956$, $p = 0.004$), suggesting that nutritional status varied across these demographic categories.

These findings suggest that nutritional status among the elderly population was influenced by selected demographic factors, particularly civil status, age, and barangay of residence.

Part 4. Significant Differences in Malnutrition Risk by Demographic Profile

This study also sought to determine whether significant differences existed in the malnutrition risk among elderly respondents from selected barangays of San Mariano when grouped according to their profile variables. To address this objective, a Chi-square Test of Independence was performed to assess the association between malnutrition risk and the respondents' demographic characteristics. In cases where significant associations were identified, post hoc Bonferroni tests were subsequently conducted to pinpoint specific group differences while controlling for Type I error. Table 5 below summarizes the relationships between malnutrition risk and key profile variables specifically age, sex, civil status, ethnicity, and place of residence.

Table 5.

Chi-Square Test of Independence on the Risk of Malnutrition Among the Elderly from selected Barangays of San Mariano Grouped According to Profile Variables

Sex		Malnutrition Risk			
		Normal (No Risk)	At Risk	Malnourished	Total
Male	f	116	73	5	194
	%	21.6%	13.6%	0.9%	36.2%
Female	f	169	147	26	342
	%	31.5%	27.4%	4.9%	63.8%
Total	f	285	220	31	536
	%	53.2%	41.0%	5.8%	100.0%

Computed $X^2 = 8.776$ (df = 2) (p=0.012) significance at 5% level

Civil Status		Malnutrition Risk			
		Normal (No Risk)	At Risk	Malnourished	Total
Single	f	4	3	0	7
	%	0.7%	0.6%	0.0%	1.3%
Married	f	256	180	23	459
	%	47.8%	33.6%	4.3%	85.6%
Widow/Widower	f	25	37	8	70
	%	4.7%	6.9%	1.5%	13.1%
Total	f	285	220	31	536
	%	53.2%	41.0%	5.8%	100.0%

Computed $X^2 = 12.112$ (df = 4) (p = 0.017) significance at 5% level

Age		Malnutrition Risk			
		Normal (No Risk)	At Risk	Malnourished	Total
60-69	f	175	107	12	294
	%	32.6%	20.0%	2.2%	54.9%
70-79	f	88	77	9	174
	%	16.4%	14.4%	1.7%	32.5%
80-89	f	22	33	9	64
	%	4.1%	6.2%	1.7%	11.9%
90 and above	f	0	3	1	4
	%	0.0%	0.6%	0.2%	0.7%
Total	f	285	220	31	536
	%	53.2%	41.0%	5.8%	100.0%

Computed $X^2 = 25.388$ (df = 6) (p=0.001) significance at 5% level

Residence		Malnutrition Risk			Total
		Normal (No Risk)	At Risk	Malnourished	
Bitabian	f	38	59	13	110
	%	7.1%	11.0%	2.4%	20.5%
Binatug	f	18	28	7	53
	%	3.4%	5.2%	1.3%	9.9%
Casala	f	104	73	9	186
	%	19.4%	13.6%	1.7%	34.7%
Gangalan	f	77	43	1	121
	%	14.4%	8.0%	0.2%	22.6%
Ueg	f	48	17	1	66
	%	9.0%	3.2%	0.2%	12.3%
Total	f	285	220	31	536
	%	53.2%	41.0%	5.8%	100.0%

Computed $X^2 = 48.683$ (df = 8) (p=0.001) significance at 5% level

Ethnicity		Malnutrition Risk			Total
		Normal (No Risk)	At Risk	Malnourished	
Ilocano	f	229	174	21	424
	%	42.7%	32.5%	3.9%	79.1%
Ybanag	f	39	37	5	81
	%	7.3%	6.9%	0.9%	15.1%
Ifugao	f	10	4	2	16
	%	1.9%	0.7%	0.4%	3.0%
Agta	f	1	2	1	4
	%	0.2%	0.4%	0.2%	0.7%
Tagalog	f	6	3	2	11
	%	1.1%	0.6%	0.4%	2.1%
Total	f	285	220	31	536
	%	53.2%	41.0%	5.8%	100.0%

Computed $X^2 = 10.570$ (df = 8) (p=0.227) significance at 5% level

The results revealed a statistically significant difference in malnutrition risk when respondents were grouped according to sex (χ^2 (2) = 8.776, p = 0.012). Post hoc analysis using the Bonferroni correction indicated that female respondents differed significantly from male respondents. As shown in table 5., both the prevalence and risk of malnutrition were higher among females (4.9% and 27.4%, respectively) compared to males (0.9% and 13.6%).

Similarly, civil status showed a significant difference in malnutrition risk (χ^2 (4) = 12.112, p = 0.017). Bonferroni post hoc comparisons revealed that married respondents differed significantly from other civil status groups. Notably, married elderly individuals exhibited the highest prevalence and risk of malnutrition, at 4.3% and 33.6%, respectively.

With respect to age, the results demonstrated a significant difference in malnutrition risk across age groups (χ^2 (4) = 25.388, p = 0.001). Further analysis showed that respondents aged 60–69 years differed significantly from other age groups and recorded the highest prevalence (2.2%) and risk (20%) of malnutrition.

A significant difference in malnutrition risk was also observed based on place of residence ($\chi^2 (8) = 48.683, p = 0.001$). Bonferroni post hoc analysis indicated that respondents from Barangay Bitabian differed significantly from those residing in other barangays. Barangay Bitabian recorded the highest prevalence of malnutrition at 2.7% (f = 13), while the highest prevalence of malnutrition risk was observed in Barangay Casala at 13.6% (f = 73), followed by Barangay Bitabian at 11.0% (f = 59).

In contrast, no statistically significant difference in malnutrition risk was found when respondents were grouped according to ethnicity ($\chi^2 (8) = 10.570, p = 0.227$). Nonetheless, descriptive results indicated that the Ilocano ethnic group recorded the highest prevalence of malnutrition (3.9%, f = 21) and malnutrition risk (32.5%, f = 174), as shown in table above.

Part 5. Proposed Program to Prevent Progressive Malnutrition Among the Elderly of San Mariano

Nutrition programs are planned actions that aim to improve nutrition-related behaviors, health, and environmental conditions. These programs intended to positively change or improve nutrition related problems identified based on the above findings. This study conducted nutrition screening and determined malnutrition risk among selected elderly population and identify the determinants related to elderly malnutrition (See Recommendations section below).

DISCUSSION

This study sought to determine malnutrition risk among the elderly population in selected San Mariano barangays and determine whether significant differences exists among the determinants of malnutrition (decline in food intake, involuntary weight loss, mobility, presence of psychological stress or acute disease, neuropsychological conditions and body mass index) as well as malnutrition risk (no risk or minimal risk, at risk and malnourished) when grouped according to profile variables of the respondents specifically age, gender, civil status, ethnicity, and place of residence.

I. Demographic Profile of Respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents provides essential context for understanding the nutritional and health conditions of the elderly population in the selected barangays of San Mariano. The predominance of female respondents reflects global and national aging patterns, where women tend to live longer than men. Recent studies have emphasized that older women often face greater nutritional vulnerability due to longer life expectancy, higher likelihood of living alone, and increased exposure to socioeconomic and health-related risks in later life (World Health Organization, 2021).

The high proportion of married respondents suggests that many elderly individuals remain within family-based living arrangements. Social and marital support has been

shown to play a crucial role in shaping dietary behaviors, access to food, and utilization of health services among older adults. Recent evidence highlights that elderly individuals with stronger household and social support systems generally experience better nutritional and health outcomes, although this support may vary depending on household dynamics and caregiving capacity (Silva et al., 2022; WHO, 2022).

The age composition of the respondents indicates that most belong to the younger segment of the elderly population. Contemporary gerontological literature underscores that early old age is a critical period for preventive interventions, as functional decline, chronic disease, and nutritional risk often begin to emerge during this stage. Addressing nutritional concerns early can help delay or prevent more severe health complications later in life (Beard et al., 2021).

Differences in residence across barangays point to the influence of geographic and environmental factors on elderly health and nutrition. Access to health care, food systems, transportation, and basic services varies across communities and has been identified as a key determinant of nutritional well-being among older adults. Community-level disparities reinforce the need for localized and context-specific interventions to effectively address elderly malnutrition (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2023; WHO, 2021).

The ethnic composition of the respondents reflects the broader sociocultural landscape of San Mariano. While ethnicity alone may not directly determine nutritional status, cultural practices, food preferences, language, and social inclusion can influence dietary behaviors and engagement with health and nutrition programs. Recent public health literature emphasizes the importance of culturally sensitive approaches when designing interventions for diverse elderly populations (UNICEF, 2021; WHO, 2022).

Overall, the demographic profile highlights the importance of adopting a gender-sensitive, age-responsive, and community-based approach in addressing elderly nutrition. Understanding these demographic characteristics enables policymakers and health practitioners to design targeted interventions that are responsive to the social, cultural, and environmental realities of the elderly population, thereby supporting healthy aging and reducing the risk of nutrition-related decline.

II. Malnutrition Risk of the Respondents

The prevalence of malnutrition and the higher proportion of older adults who are at risk of developing malnutrition (nutritionally-at-risk) in selected barangays of San Mariano are consistent with national findings among community-dwelling Filipino elderly, where nutritional risk is more common than overt malnutrition. Studies published in *Acta Medica Philippines* from 2020 to 2022 have documented similar patterns, reporting low-to-moderate prevalence of undernutrition but substantially higher rates of nutritional risk (Navarro et. al., 2020; Cruz et. al., 2022 and Padilla et. al., 2022)

A systematic review and meta-analysis conducted among older adults in Thailand reported that pooled malnutrition-risk prevalence was approximately 42.6%, with malnutrition prevalence around 6.1% using the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA) instrument (Chuansangeam et al., 2022). In Indonesia, a 2022 systematic review found that risk-of-malnutrition rates commonly exceeded 40% across studies of community-dwelling older adults (Dewiasty et al., 2022). Globally, malnutrition and malnutrition risk also remain as a significant concern among older adults. These findings parallel earlier studies from Lebanon, Sri Lanka, and India which demonstrated substantial at-risk populations despite differing social contexts.

Variations in malnutrition risk across the five barangays highlight the influence of environmental, socioeconomic, and health system factors on elderly nutritional status. While most of the older adult population maintained normal nutritional status, the presence of nutritionally at-risk and malnourished individuals indicates that malnutrition remains a public health concern that needs to be addressed. Barangays with better access to food, health services, and social support appear more capable of sustaining adequate nutrition, whereas others that face structural barriers that increase vulnerability. These disparities underscore the importance of localized interventions, including routine nutrition screening, targeted support, and improved access to health and nutrition services among the barangays.

III. Malnutrition Determinants based on the Revised Mini Nutritional Assessment - Short Form

A. Determinants of Malnutrition among the Respondents

The findings of this study demonstrate that malnutrition among elderly residents of selected barangays in San Mariano is a multifactorial condition shaped by interrelated dietary, physiological, functional, social, and environmental determinants. The analysis highlights that nutritional vulnerability often develops gradually and is influenced by both individual-level factors and broader community contexts.

Decline in food intake over recent months emerged as one of the strongest determinants of malnutrition. Malnourished respondents consistently reported reduced dietary consumption, underscoring inadequate intake as a primary pathway to undernutrition in older adults. This finding aligns with existing evidence that insufficient energy and nutrient intake directly compromises health, immune function, and physical capacity among the elderly (Beard et al., 2021; Ganhão-Arranhado et al., 2023). Reduced intake may stem from poor appetite, difficulty chewing or swallowing, limited food availability, or decreased ability to prepare meals—factors commonly experienced in aging populations.

Involuntary weight loss was another prominent determinant observed among malnourished respondents, confirming its role as a critical indicator of nutritional decline. Weight loss in older adults is often multifactorial, resulting from prolonged inadequate intake, chronic disease burden, or metabolic changes, and is strongly associated with

functional impairment and increased morbidity (Kim et al., 2025). Notably, some malnourished individuals did not report recent psychological stress or acute illness, suggesting that malnutrition may progress silently and remain unrecognized until more advanced stages.

Functional limitations, particularly reduced mobility, were frequently present among malnourished respondents. Mobility impairment can restrict food access, grocery shopping, meal preparation, and even the act of eating itself, thereby reinforcing nutritional deficits. Similarly, the presence of neuropsychological conditions such as mild cognitive impairment or dementia among some respondents further increased vulnerability, as cognitive decline can impair appetite regulation, meal planning, and adherence to adequate dietary practices (Ribeiro et al., 2023).

Body mass index (BMI) was also identified as a significant determinant, with lower BMI observed among those at risk of malnutrition or already malnourished. Low BMI remains a widely accepted marker of chronic energy deficiency and potential muscle mass loss in older adults, both of which are predictors of frailty, disability, and adverse health outcomes (Ganhão-Arranhado et al., 2023). These findings reinforce the importance of monitoring anthropometric indicators alongside dietary and functional assessments.

Sociodemographic factors further influenced nutritional status among the elderly in this study. Malnutrition was more prevalent among female respondents, consistent with recent research indicating sex-related differences in nutritional risk among older adults (Ganhão-Arranhado et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2023). Gender-related differences in longevity, functional limitations, and social determinants may contribute to this pattern, as females generally live longer and experience more age-related functional decline that increases vulnerability to nutritional deficiencies (Ganhão-Arranhado et al., 2023). However, evidence suggests that sex interacts with other socioeconomic and health factors rather than acting alone to determine nutritional outcomes.

Age was a significant determinant, with malnutrition risk rising with advancing age, mirroring recent findings that older age groups face higher nutritional vulnerability due to physiological changes such as sarcopenia and increased chronic disease burden. Although some studies have focused on institutionalized populations, community-dwelling elderly are similarly at risk of nutritional decline (Ganhão-Arranhado et al., 2023).

Civil status was significantly associated with malnutrition risk, with married respondents showing the highest prevalence, a finding that contrasts with some studies that generally identify marriage as protective through enhanced social support. This divergence suggests that marital status alone does not adequately reflect the quality of social support or caregiving dynamics, necessitating further exploration of household and relational factors in nutritional outcomes.

Place of residence emerged as a strong determinant of malnutrition, with significant inter-barangay variations reflecting differences in food access, income, and

service availability. These patterns align with community studies that highlight how environmental determinants influence elderly nutritional status (Shuremu et. al., 2023). Conversely, ethnicity was not significantly associated with nutritional status in this study, potentially reflecting shared dietary practices and living conditions that attenuate ethnic disparities observed elsewhere.

Overall, the findings emphasize that elderly malnutrition in San Mariano results from a complex interplay of dietary inadequacy, sociodemographic characteristics, and environmental factors. The high proportion of older adults at risk for developing malnutrition underscores the importance of early nutrition screening and assessment for an integrated community intervention to promote healthy aging.

B. Differences in Malnutrition Determinants When Grouped According to Profile

The study examined whether key determinants of malnutrition among elderly respondents—such as decline in food intake, involuntary weight loss, mobility limitations, psychological stress, neuropsychiatric problems, and body mass index (BMI)—differed significantly across demographic characteristics of sex, age, civil status, place of residence, and ethnicity.

The results indicated that decline in food intake varied significantly across several demographic factors. Certain groups were more likely to experience reduced dietary intake, suggesting that demographic characteristics such as sex, marital status, age, and residential location influence eating patterns and access to adequate nutrition among older adults. These findings are consistent with recent literature highlighting the interplay between social, physiological, and environmental factors in shaping nutritional behavior in elderly populations (Beard et al., 2021; Ganhão-Arranhado et al., 2023).

In contrast, other determinants—such as involuntary weight loss, mobility limitations, psychological stress, and neuropsychiatric conditions—were relatively uniform across all demographic categories. This suggests that while some aspects of nutritional risk are closely tied to individual characteristics, other health-related factors may affect elderly individuals more broadly, independent of demographic differences.

Meanwhile, Body Mass Index (BMI), a critical indicator of nutritional status, showed significant differences based on civil status, age, and place of residence. This finding is comparable a previous study by Camilo et. al in 2024 where older age and being single was attributed to having a lower BMI. In addition, Pan and Hao (2025) found that body mass index among Chinese older adults varied by urban–rural residence and was linked to multidimensional health outcomes.

The findings shows that elderly individuals from certain demographic groups appear more vulnerable to undernutrition due to the cumulative effects of physiological changes, social circumstances, and environmental influences.

IV. Differences in Malnutrition Risk When Grouped According to Profile

The study examined whether malnutrition risk among elderly respondents varied according to key demographic characteristics, including sex, civil status, age, place of residence, and ethnicity. The analysis revealed significant differences in malnutrition risk across several demographic factors, indicating that nutritional vulnerability is influenced by both individual and contextual characteristics.

Sex was significantly associated with malnutrition risk, with female respondents showing higher risk compared to males. This aligns with recent evidence that older women are more susceptible to nutritional deficiencies, potentially due to sex-specific physiological and health factors (Ghabashi & Azzeh, 2024)

Civil status also demonstrated significant differences, with married elderly individuals exhibiting higher malnutrition risk compared to other groups. This may reflect complex interactions between family dynamics, caregiving responsibilities, and dietary practices within households. Similar patterns have been observed in other community-based studies, highlighting the role of social support and household composition in shaping nutritional outcomes among older adults (Tsang et al., 2025).

Age was another factor associated with significant variation in malnutrition risk, with younger elderly respondents differing from older age groups. Age-related physiological changes, including declines in appetite, digestive efficiency, and physical function, contribute to increased nutritional vulnerability in older adults (Rolland et al., 2022).

Place of residence also influenced malnutrition risk, suggesting that community-level factors such as food accessibility, healthcare availability, and socioeconomic conditions may affect elderly nutrition. Certain barangays had higher prevalence and risk, highlighting the importance of localized assessments and targeted interventions to address environmental and social determinants of malnutrition (Ganhão-Arranhado et al., 2023).

In contrast, ethnicity did not show a statistically significant difference in malnutrition risk, although descriptive trends indicated higher prevalence among the majority ethnic group. This suggests that while cultural and dietary practices may influence nutrition, other demographic and environmental factors exert a stronger effect on malnutrition risk in this population.

Overall, the findings underscore that malnutrition among the elderly is shaped by a combination of individual, social, and community-level determinants. These results highlight the need for targeted interventions that consider sex, age, civil status, and residential context to effectively prevent malnutrition and promote healthy aging in community-dwelling older adults. Routine nutritional screening, community-based education, and context-specific support programs are recommended to mitigate these disparities and support optimal nutritional health

V. Proposed Nutrition Program for Elderly Malnutrition

The San Mariano Lingap Nutrisyon at Malusog na Pagtanda (SLN-MP) Program represents a comprehensive, community-based response to malnutrition among elderly residents of San Mariano, Isabela. Anchored on the findings of this study, the program is designed to address both the prevalence of malnutrition risk and the multiple determinants that contribute to poor nutritional status among older adults. By integrating nutrition-specific and nutrition-sensitive interventions, SLN-MP adopts a holistic approach that targets immediate nutritional deficits while also addressing underlying physiological, social, and environmental factors.

A core component of the program is early identification through routine nutritional screening, which responds directly to the study's finding that a substantial proportion of the elderly are already at nutritional risk, even before overt malnutrition becomes evident. Systematic screening enables the timely identification of malnourished and at-risk individuals, allowing interventions to be targeted to those most in need and preventing further nutritional deterioration. This approach is supported by evidence showing that early detection is critical in reducing functional decline, morbidity, and adverse health outcomes among older adults (Ganhão Arranhado et al., 2023).

In response to the observed decline in food intake, involuntary weight loss, and low BMI among respondents, SLN-MP incorporates targeted supplemental feeding and micronutrient support to directly improve dietary adequacy. These interventions are complemented by nutrition education and behavior change activities aimed at empowering elderly individuals and their caregivers with practical knowledge and skills to sustain healthy eating practices. Such combined strategies are consistent with best practices in community-based nutrition programs, which emphasize that sustainable improvements in elderly nutrition require both direct support and informed behavioral change,

Recognizing the strong association between malnutrition, limited structured physical activity interventions, such as walking, dance, and yoga. These activities are intended to maintain mobility, preserve muscle strength, and enhance overall quality of life. In addition, improved access to healthcare services—through PhilHealth enrollment, free laboratory tests, and provision of essential medicines—addresses underlying health conditions that exacerbate nutritional vulnerability. Additionally, oral health interventions, including the provision of dentures, further support adequate food intake by improving chewing ability, acknowledging the critical link between oral function and nutrition in older adults.

Beyond individual-level interventions, SLN-MP integrates nutrition-sensitive strategies that respond to broader social and environmental determinants of malnutrition identified in the study. Livelihood and food security initiatives, such as community gardening, aim to improve food availability and dietary diversity, particularly in barangays with higher concentrations of nutritionally at-risk elderly.

The program is further justified by the study's identification of demographic disparities in malnutrition risk, including differences by sex, age group, civil status, and place of residence. Higher risk among female respondents, certain age groups, married individuals, and residents of specific barangays highlights the necessity of targeted and context-sensitive interventions rather than a one-size-fits-all approach. By tailoring strategies to local needs and vulnerabilities, SLN-MP seeks to reduce inequities in nutritional outcomes among the elderly population.

Overall, the SLN-MP program is designed to promote early detection of malnutrition, improve dietary intake, address functional and health-related determinants, and strengthen community support systems for healthy aging. Its integrated, community-based framework reflects the multifactorial nature of elderly malnutrition identified in this study and emphasizes the importance of coordinated health, nutrition, and social interventions. Implementing this program is expected to reduce nutrition-related morbidity, enhance functional independence, and improve the overall well-being and quality of life of older adults in San Mariano.

Conclusions

This study investigated the determinants of malnutrition and malnutrition risk among the elderly in selected barangays of San Mariano, Isabela, in relation to their demographic profiles.

The findings revealed that malnutrition among the elderly is multifactorial, influenced by dietary, physiological, functional, social, and environmental factors. Key contributors included reduced food intake, involuntary weight loss, low body mass index, limited mobility, and neuropsychological conditions.

Analysis of differences according to profile showed that malnutrition determinants varied significantly across sex, age, civil status, and place of residence, particularly in dietary patterns and body mass index. Similarly, malnutrition risk differed significantly according to these demographic factors, with female respondents and residents of certain barangays exhibiting higher vulnerability. In contrast, ethnicity did not significantly affect either determinants or risk.

These results lead to the rejection of both null hypotheses: (1) There is no significant difference in the determinants of malnutrition among the elderly when grouped according to demographic profile and (2) There is no significant difference in malnutrition risk among the elderly when grouped according to demographic profile.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions above, the study recommends the conduct of routine nutritional screening using validated tools such as the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA®) should be institutionalized at the barangay and municipal levels to enable early identification and management of malnutrition among the elderly.

Second, barangay-specific, community-based nutrition interventions should be implemented, particularly in areas with higher malnutrition risk, integrating nutrition education, dietary supplementation, physical activity promotion, and access to essential health services.

Third, future studies should include all barangays in San Mariano and utilize probability sampling and mixed-method approaches to improve generalizability and better explore the underlying determinants of elderly malnutrition.

Fourth, comprehensive nutritional assessment tools should be used in future research (such as the Mini Nutritional Assessment) in addition to screening instruments to support more effective program planning and intervention design.

Fifth, involvement or engagement of local communities through outreach and programs, workshops and community health promotion events are imperative. National and local health systems should collaborate in raising awareness about the consequence of progressive undernutrition in elderly.

Next, the findings of this study should be used to inform the development or strengthening of local and national food and nutrition policies for the elderly. Further community-based research is recommended to examine the relationship between nutrition, quality of life, and public health interventions among older adults in the Local context.

This study also recommends the implementation of the proposed program below:

Proposed Program to Prevent Progressive Malnutrition Among the Elderly of San Mariano

Program Title: SANMARIANONG Lingap Nutrisyon at Malusog na Pagtanda (SLN-MP), *A Comprehensive Community-Based Program to Prevent Progressive Malnutrition Among the Elderly San Marianinos*

Program Description

The San Mariano Lingap Nutrisyon at Malusog na Pagtanda (SLN-MP) is an integrated, community-based nutrition and healthy aging program designed to prevent progressive malnutrition among elderly San Marianinos. Anchored on the findings of this present study, which identified the prevalence of malnutrition and malnutrition risk among the senior citizens, the program adopts a life-course and multisectoral approach that combines nutrition-specific and nutrition sensitive interventions in one program.

This program emphasizes early detection through routine nutritional screening, nutrition education and behavior change, food and micronutrient supplementation, and healthcare access strengthening. Complementary strategies include the promotion of physical activity, livelihood-based food security initiatives, access to safe water and sanitation, oral health services, and financial risk protection through PhilHealth

enrollment. Collectively, these interventions aim to improve dietary intake, prevent functional decline, reduce nutrition-related morbidity and mortality, and promote healthy and dignified aging within the community.

General Objective

To improve the nutritional health and overall well-being of elderly San Marianinos through integrated nutrition education, food and micronutrient supplementation, improved access to healthcare services and healthy lifestyle promotion

Program Components and Key Strategies

Key Program Component	Major Activities	Target Beneficiaries	Implementing Agencies	Time Frame	Expected Outcomes
Nutritional Screening	Routine biannual nutrition screening GO Hatid Sigla at Sustansya Para Kila Lolo at Lola	All senior citizens	RHU, BNS, BHWs	Feb & July	Early identification of at-risk elderly
Supplemental Nutrition	IEC development and lectures	Malnourished and at-risk elderly	RHU, BNS, BHCs	Apr–Jun	Improved nutrition status
Nutrition Education	HL to the Max	Senior citizens and caregivers	RHU, OSCA	Year-round	Improved nutrition knowledge and behaviors
Physical Activity	Hatid eKon Para sa SC	All senior citizens	RHU, OSCA	Year-round	Improved mobility and functional health
Health Access	Free labs and medicines	Financially at-risk elderly	RHU, OSCA, MSWDO	Year-round	Reduced health financial burden
Medical Support	Balik Ngiti sa SC	Malnourished elderly	RHU, BHCs	Year-round	Improved health outcomes
Oral Health	Gulayan for All	Malnourished elderly	RHU	Apr–May	Improved food intake
Livelihood		At-risk elderly	MAO, partners	Apr–Jun	Improved food security

Expected Outcomes

- a. Early identifications of malnourished and nutritionally-at-risk elderly
- b. Improved dietary intake and nutritional status among program beneficiaries
- c. Improved functional capacity, mobility and quality of life
- d. Strengthened family and community support systems for healthy aging.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author upheld the moral principles of beneficence, respect, integrity and protection of the participants and followed the prevailing ethical practices relevant to the conduct of the study.

The study included the 536 elderly participants from five selected barangays of San Mariano. The researcher gave high regard to the participants and enumerators by ensuring their safety and security during the conduct of the study. Both enumerators and study participants underwent briefing and explanation of the study's purpose, data collection procedure, and the reasons why they were chosen. Furthermore, participants were assured that their participation in the study was voluntary and that they had the right to refuse to participate in the data collection process. They were given ample time to ask questions about their involvement in the study, and had the option to withdraw if they felt unsafe, uncomfortable, or hesitant to provide information for the study. Furthermore, participants were informed that they were not obliged or forced to participate in the study, and that there would be no negative consequences if they chose not to participate.

A written informed consent form was provided and signed with the participants' and their caregivers' voluntary consent in order to reach a just agreement between the researcher and the participants. It provided information about the following: (1) the purpose of the research, (2) study procedure, (3) potential risks and discomfort, (4) potential benefits, (5) confidentiality, and (6) participation or withdrawal from the research process.

The researcher also considered the psychological vulnerability of the participants. In this situation, the researcher gave assurance to the participants of full confidentiality, and their identity was kept anonymous in the research instrument, analysis, and reporting of the findings. To address the participants' apprehension which might affect their true and honest responses, the researcher emphasized the benefits they could get when they provide truthful answers in the survey questionnaire.

Some participants may have found some of the survey questionnaire items very personal, while others may have felt uncomfortable and anxious about disclosing their true answers. In these cases, the participants were reminded that they had the right and freedom to refuse to answer the survey. In addition, they were allowed to openly ask questions about the study and were assured that they will not be harmed in any way. It was also reiterated that the empirical results and analysis of this study will be beneficial not only for them but for the whole community of San Mariano, as it will serve as a baseline

data gathering mechanism for program and preparation to address elderly malnutrition and improve the quality of life among the senior citizens in San Mariano.

The researcher diligently protected the participants' privacy. In accordance with the Data-Privacy Act of 2012, or R.A.10173, the confidentiality of information obtained from participants were maintained. To ensure the participants' anonymity, no personal information was disclosed. Raw data were properly disposed of through manual shredding, and all electronic copies will be deleted after processing. Transparency was also ensured by conducting a thorough briefing to the participants where the nature and purpose of the study, as well as the scope of their participation were explained.

Community involvement in this research endeavor was highlighted with the participation of the senior citizens from the selected barangays and the support for demand generation by the municipal and barangay nutrition council members. In return, the researcher will be publishing the findings from the study once feasible and share it with the community and major stakeholders involved.

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